

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

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Report on the establishment of the Living Lab

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Abstract	This deliverable documents the establishment of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) on Bornholm, Denmark. It outlines the conceptual foundations, co-creation processes, stakeholder engagement, implementation activities, and evaluation framework used to develop the Living Lab. Guided by New European Bauhaus values and Living Lab principles, the HGLL connects craft heritage with circular economy experimentation, positioning Bornholm as a “test island” for sustainable innovation in the craft sector.
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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
HGLL	HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab
LL / LLS	Living Lab / Living Labs
NEB	New European Bauhaus
HAM	Harmonized Assessment Methodology

About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long-lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

- Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.
- Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.
- Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.
- Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.
- Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.
- Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value-added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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Executive Summary

This report details the establishment of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) on the Danish island of Bornholm—an initiative that unites craft-makers, researchers, municipalities, and other regional stakeholders in co-creating sustainable solutions for the future of European craft. The Green Living Lab represents a practical, real-world environment where novel approaches to craft and resource use can be tested, evaluated, and refined. Building on Bornholm’s “test island” identity and the island’s strong craft tradition, the HGLL aims to foster both technological and creative innovation, while anchoring outcomes in local realities.

Informed by the values and working principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB), such as sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics, the HGLL advances the project’s ambition of making European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically resilient. Stakeholder engagement processes, which have involved local craft networks, heritage institutions, and policymakers, ensure that the solutions developed are both relevant and widely supported. Activities such as circular material experimentation, participatory workshops, international symposia, and collaborative research have all helped align the lab’s objectives with real-world opportunities and constraints.

Through a series of co-creation events—including the symposium in Dals Långed, Sweden, and multiple workshops on Bornholm—participants explored key challenges in craft production, from seasonality and financial viability to waste reuse and new technology adoption. The final outcome of these discussions directly shaped the HGLL’s action plan and its thematic focus on environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Flagship initiatives, such as crushing ceramic waste into material for new glazes, reusing waste cooking oil to fire kilns, and designing sustainable tourism opportunities, illustrate how practical, creative experimentation can align with municipal circular economy visions.

Looking ahead, the HGLL will continue to evolve and expand its stakeholder base, guided by an iterative framework of living lab principles—co-creation, experimentation, evaluation, and scale-up. The results and learnings generated by the lab will feed into broader policy dialogues and strategic planning both in Bornholm and across the HEPHAESTUS partner regions. In this way, the establishment of the HGLL stands as a replicable model for how cultural heritage, local governance, and emerging technologies can come together to revitalize craft—and, in turn, drive circular innovation for Europe’s creative sectors.

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1. Purpose and Structure of the Report

This section of the report outlines the structure of the document. The structure follows the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab model (Figure 1), across four overarching phases: **Co-creation with stakeholders; Implementation; Evaluation; and Policy dialogue & Scale up**. While guiding the overarching management and facilitation of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab, the model is used in this document as a reference point for our description of the establishment process. It is important to note that, in line with the iterative nature of the process, activities in the different phases might have overlapped over time. Additionally, while activities are described in separate sections, they are interconnected and continuously inform each other.

Figure 1 HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab Model

The first phase – **Co-creation with Stakeholders** – involves engaging various stakeholders in a collaborative process to analyse scenarios, ideate, and co-design solutions (see D5.1 and D4.1). This phase was kickstarted in February 2023 covering e.g. engagement with key craft ecosystem stakeholders on Bornholm, and includes the following:

- **Analysis of Scenario:** Understanding the current context of the HGLL and identifying challenges, opportunities, needs and expectations.
- **Ideation:** Generating creative ideas through brainstorming and focus groups.
- **Co-design:** Collaboratively developing solutions with various stakeholders, primarily the craft ambassadors.
- **Interviews & Questionnaires:** Gathering insights and feedback to inform the design process of the HGLL.

The second phase – **Implementation** – was kickstarted in early March 2025 with the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab launch event of the exhibition “*Ødeland*”, the work of which had been underway for a number of months prior. Throughout the implementation phase, the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab activities will be put into practice through various initiatives such as this, aimed at engaging the community and testing ideas. These activities are elaborated on in detail in Section 4.2. This phase is characterized by its experimental nature and driven by the co-creation activities which informed the nature of the implementation. All are within the framework of the HEPHAESTUS mission: “*to research, preserve, and innovate craft sectors to deliver a cutting-edge, creative, and sustainable technology-driven economy based on cultural heritage*”. These implementation activities include (but are not limited to):

- **Workshops:** Conducting hands-on sessions to develop and refine solutions.
- **Events:** Organizing events to showcase and test the solutions with a broader audience.
- **Community Engagement:** Involving the community in the implementation process to ensure relevance and buy-in. This also includes communication activities and maintaining an online presence to promote the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab.
- **Exhibitions:** Displaying the outcomes and progress to gather further feedback and promote awareness.

The third phase – **Evaluation** – focuses on assessing the effectiveness and impact of the HGLL. For this, a Harmonized Assessment Methodology (HAM) has been developed which derives its process indicators from Femmer et al’s (2019) Living Lab principles, applied to the HGLL and which were first introduced in D5.1. The full evaluation of the HGLL solutions by end-users will be described in detail in D5.5 (M44).

Finally, the fourth phase - **Policy Dialogue & Scale-up** - involves using the insights gained from the previous phases to inform policy discussions and scale up successful solutions. A crucial aspect of this phase is the establishment of the HEPHAESTUS vision think tank (see D5.4) involving key stakeholders from the Bornholm ecosystem and beyond, including but not limited to craftmakers, BOFA and the Regional Municipality of Bornholm at large, Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB), and the Royal Academy. This will play a vital role in bridging the gap between experimentation, research and policy implementation by offering evidence-based recommendations and fostering informed discussions and collaboration.

Based on this premise, the document is structured as follows:

- *Section 2: Origins and Conceptual Premises* outlines the theoretical and strategic foundations of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). Drawing from D5.1 and the New European Bauhaus (NEB) Toolbox, it explores Living Lab methodologies, NEB alignment, and design principles that inform the HGLL’s development.
- *Section 3: Co-Creation Activities* describes the participatory processes that shaped the HGLL’s focus areas, including international symposia, workshops, and focus groups. These co-creation events provided the foundation for the Living Lab’s implementation tracks.

- *Section 4:* Implementation details the ongoing HGLL initiatives, each rooted in real-world challenges and driven by stakeholder engagement. The section includes thematic tracks such as circular craft practices, digital storytelling, sustainable tourism, and infrastructural experimentation. It also reflects on the Living Lab’s evolving identity, stakeholder coordination, and interdisciplinary character.
- *Section 5:* Evaluation introduces the Harmonized Assessment Methodology (HAM), a reflexive evaluation framework based on Living Lab principles and NEB values. It outlines the process indicators used to monitor progress, inclusion, and impact across the HGLL.
- *Section 6:* Policy Dialogue & Scale-up presents the emerging governance and policy coordination mechanisms that support long-term impact. It introduces the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank (detailed further in D5.4) as a key vehicle for anchoring Living Lab outcomes in institutional structures and broader circular economy transitions.

2. The HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab

This section introduces the conceptual foundations and strategic framing of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). It outlines how the idea of Bornholm as a “test island” for circular economy has shaped the lab’s formation, and situates the HGLL within the broader theoretical landscapes of Living Lab methodology and the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative.

Building on the early groundwork laid in D5.1 and informed by participatory dialogue with local stakeholders, this chapter traces the evolution of the HGLL from contextual inspiration to a structured, value-driven framework for experimentation. Section 2.1 describes the origins and enabling conditions for the HGLL, while Section 2.2 elaborates on the values, design principles, and frameworks—drawn from NEB and Living Lab literature—that guide its implementation and ongoing activities.

2.1 Building the HGLL: Bornholm’s Test Island Context

The process towards the establishment of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) officially started in February 2023, with the first call for craft ambassadors in the Bornholm craft ecosystem aimed at establishing the network of craft makers, exploring synergies between their work and the HEPHAESTUS objectives. HEPHAESTUS D5.1 “*Report on establishment of the network of municipalities, heritage sites and museums, participating at the Living Lab*” (Zingenberg and Kjærgaard Knudsen, 2023) presents the conceptual basis of the Living Lab, as well as the contextual factors that have shaped preliminary participatory activities in Bornholm. Here it has been put forth that the HGLL benefits from multiple synergies deriving from BOFA’s ambition of offering up Bornholm as a “test island” for circular economy and sustainability (Manniche & Hansen, 2023), bridging with the craft sector - an important aspect of the Bornholm’s cultural heritage and economy (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022; Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2023), a stronghold position in its tourism development and a cornerstone of the endeavor to eliminate waste incineration on the Island by 2032 (BOFA, 2019; BOFA, 2022). This vision aligns with the Bright Green Island strategy (Mikkola, Randall, & Hagberg, 2016), positioning Bornholm as a real-world laboratory for waste prevention, reuse, and recycling.

The “test island” proposition designates Bornholm as a controlled yet real-life environment for experimenting with sustainable solutions at a regional scale. Bornholm’s geographic and social characteristics—self-contained systems, a strong local identity, and an engaged citizenry—make it an ideal setting for circular economy trials. The Living Lab approach enhances this by ensuring collaboration between local actors, businesses, and researchers, emphasizing participatory innovation and real-world implementation.

The HGLL capitalizes on different Bornholm and BOFA-driven (though not exclusively so) initiatives spanning multiple domains of circularity and green transition. For example,

- **EcoGrid 2.0** (Horizon 2020) demonstrated energy flexibility through consumer participation.
- **Wasteman** (Interreg South Baltic) tested citizen-driven waste sorting systems.
- **SYMSITES** (Horizon Europe) integrates industrial and urban symbiosis, using food and wastewater streams for local production.
- **CEBW** (LIFE-Integrated) focuses on white goods repair (refrigerators, etc.) collected at recycling stations and reuse, as well as building and construction waste reuse through a material bank.

These projects illustrate multiple directions of experimentation, from energy optimization to material recovery, forming an ecosystem of interrelated sustainability efforts.

The craft sector is a crucial bridge in this transition. Traditional crafts embody sustainability principles—local materials, low amounts of waste produced in the production of craft pieces, and longevity—offering models for circular production. The HGLL builds on this, engaging craft makers in repurposing waste materials and co-developing innovative circular business models. This fusion of heritage and sustainability strengthens Bornholm’s identity as a test island while demonstrating how circularity can be embedded in cultural and economic frameworks.

Together, these efforts position Bornholm as a model for other regions seeking to implement circular economies, highly topical in islands, where resources are not only recycled but fundamentally revalued and preserved through local innovation.

2.2 Core principles: New European Bauhaus (NEB) and Living Labs

The New European Bauhaus (NEB), an initiative launched by the European Commission, can play a crucial role in shaping the development of Living Labs, particularly those oriented toward sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics. Driven by the ambition of bringing together sustainability, beauty, and inclusivity in the built environment and development of cutting-edge products or services (European Commission, 2023), the NEB serves as a transdisciplinary framework that fosters participatory innovation, aligning closely with the co-creation and experimentation principles fundamental to Living Labs (European Commission, 2024).

Figure 2: NEB Values and ambitions

WORKING PRINCIPLES

Figure 3: NEB Working principles and ambitions

On this line, the EU Commission, with support from Rambøll and ICLEI, have developed the NEB toolbox (European Commission, 2023). as an instrument to support the development of NEB initiatives across the EU. As such they provide a practical guideline to support the interaction and mutual reinforcement between values (Figure 2- sustainability, beauty, and inclusiveness) and working principles (Figure 3) - like participatory processes, multi-level engagement, and a transdisciplinary approach.

Therefore, for the development of Living Labs, the NEB Toolbox can serve as a guiding framework to ensure that co-creation processes are well-structured, sustainability goals are measurable, and aesthetic and cultural values are embedded in innovation activities. By using the NEB Toolbox (European Commission, 2023), stakeholders can define clear evaluation criteria, ensuring that their Living Lab aligns with broader EU policy objectives in sustainability, circular economy, and social inclusion. Additionally, the toolbox supports the creation of tailored solutions that reflect the local identity, socio-economic context, and environmental challenges of specific communities, such as Bornholm’s Island economy. As a core objective of the HEPHAESTUS project is the development of a Living Lab, building on NEB values and working principles can facilitate new collaborations across the craft sector on Bornholm and support the transition to a circular economy, e.g. by bringing together actors withing public sector, private sector and academia in new forms of inter-collaboration. To do so, a key challenge for the HEPHAESTUS project is integrating our evolving understanding of craft (Macció & Gasparin, 2024) with NEB principles and LLs development best practices.

New European Bauhaus and the HEPHAESTUS approach to Living Labs

As introduced in Deliverable D1.2, Report for Policymakers with Strategies for Sustainable Craft Ecosystem Management and Heritage Preservation (Gasparin et al., 2023), the HEPHAESTUS project developed the HEPHAESTUS Framework to articulate a comprehensive and multidimensional understanding of craft. This framework positions craft not only as a form of manufacturing, but also as a repository of tacit knowledge, deeply rooted in historical, social, and material contexts (see Figure 4). Grounded in the project’s working definition, craft is understood as (Gasparin et al., 2024):

“...the form of manufacturing - from Latin: manus (hand) and facere (making) -in which the components of manual work, mastering of tools and technique, knowledge of the

materials meet with an intentional symbolic value, and become an object. This ranges from individual productions in small ateliers to component productions in larger manufacturing processes.”

In the context of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL), this definition underpins a collaborative ecosystem where artisans, researchers, policymakers, and local communities engage in co-creation. Together, they develop circular solutions that both safeguard craft heritage and enable innovation.

By integrating the New European Bauhaus Toolbox, the HGLL can apply structured methodologies to assess material flows, sustainable design practices, and the evolving role of craft in building resilient circular economies (Schuurman et al., 2025). This approach ensures that craft traditions are not merely preserved but actively reimagined in response to contemporary socio-economic and environmental challenges.

HEPHAESTUS FRAMEWORK

Figure 4: HEPHAESTUS framework (Gasparin et al., 2024).

NEB-Inspired Foundations for the HGLL

The HGLL builds upon a multidimensional understanding of craft, integrating traditional craftsmanship, sustainability, and digital innovation to foster circular and regenerative economies.

By working with inspiration from the NEB principles and the Living Lab principles as described by Femmer et al., 2019 (Figure 20), it establishes a framework where knowledge transmission, material experimentation, and community-driven innovation contribute to sustainable development. The following core tenets define the foundation of the HGLL, and have led to further specification of ongoing HGLL activities where practical (See Section 4.2):

Circular Craft and Sustainable Material Use

- Inspired by NEB’s focus on **sustainability and circularity**, the HGLL prioritizes bio-based, locally sourced, and upcycled materials in craft-making (European Commission, 2024b).
- **Traditional craft techniques** are reimagined within a low-carbon, circular economy framework, promoting waste reduction and resource efficiency in artisan production (Fetzer, 2025).
- The Lab functions as a **testing ground** for innovative material applications, where artisans, researchers, and designers co-develop new approaches to circular craftsmanship (see section 4.2) (Thomson, 2017).

Craft as a Knowledge System and Learning Ecosystem

- Recognizing that craft embodies both **explicit and tacit knowledge**, the Lab fosters inclusive, transdisciplinary learning environments where artisans, scholars, and policymakers collaborate (Pritchard and Koesler, 2017).
- Hands-on **training programs** integrate traditional craftsmanship with modern eco-design, digital fabrication, and parametric tools, ensuring that craft knowledge evolves while maintaining cultural authenticity (Steen & van Bueren, 2017).

Regenerative Design and Place-Based Innovation

- The Lab emphasizes **regenerative design**, ensuring that craft-making practices contribute to minimizing environmental harm (European Commission, 2024).
- A strong **place-based approach** ensures that craft innovation remains rooted in local landscapes, architectures, and socio-economic structures, reinforcing regional identities and sustainable rural development (Steen & van Bueren, 2017).
- The NEB Toolbox provides **methodologies and indicators for assessing place-based innovation strategies**, ensuring that the Lab’s outputs align with broader economic goals (European Commission, 2024).

Digital Fabrication and Craft Innovation

- The Lab acts as a **bridge between craft heritage and emerging technologies**, exploring how e.g. digital fabrication, 3D printing, and parametric design (Bögle & Popova, 2022) can enhance craftsmanship without compromising its authenticity (Fetzer, 2025).
- **Experimentation with new production models**, such as decentralized maker spaces and digital knowledge-sharing platforms, ensures greater accessibility and adaptability of craft practices (Pritchard and Koesler, 2017).

- **Technological integration supports sustainable practices** by enabling material efficiency, precision crafting, and lifecycle tracking, further aligning craft with circular economy principles (Fetzer, 2025).

3.0 Co-Creation and Stakeholder Engagement

Following the conceptual groundwork laid out in Section 2, this section turns toward the practical and social foundations of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL): stakeholder engagement and co-creation. Central to the HGLL's development is its ability to embed experimental innovation within real communities and institutions. To do so, it depends not only on technical infrastructure but on trust, participation, and locally anchored collaboration.

Section 3 outlines how the Craft Network was mobilized as the initial relational infrastructure for the Living Lab (Section 3.1), and how successive co-creation activities deepened the collaborative process across multiple dimensions of sustainability (Section 3.2). These activities, held across Sweden and Bornholm, represent iterative experiments in dialogue, material exchange, and ecosystem mapping. Importantly, they helped refine the HGLL's strategic direction while also surfacing tensions, challenges, and shared values—shaping the project's real-world implementation described in Section 4.

By tracing the evolution of engagement—from trust-building to collaborative problem-solving—this chapter highlights the Living Lab not only as a methodological tool, but as a community process grounded in participation, situated expertise, and cultural sensitivity.

3.1 The Craft Network

The Craft Network serves as the foundation for fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange within the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab. Comprising municipalities, heritage sites, museums, and other key stakeholders in the craft ecosystem, this network plays a crucial role in ensuring the successful implementation of co-creation methodologies.

As outlined in D5.1, Section 5.1, initial efforts to establish this network included a call for craft ambassadors, stakeholder engagement activities, and collaborative workshops, all of which laid the groundwork for a dynamic, interdisciplinary Living Lab. These early initiatives created a strong foundation for future expansion, ensuring that the network remains inclusive, adaptable, and responsive to the evolving needs of craft practitioners.

This section further explores how HEPHAESTUS made use of the existing network to support ongoing co-creation while also navigating and addressing challenges stemming from pre-existing stakeholder dynamics.

While the presence of a well-established craft network provided a strong platform for collaboration, it also presented challenges that needed to be addressed. Previous projects within the ecosystem had revealed instances of mistrust and dissatisfaction among some stakeholders due to imbalances in shared responsibilities, differing expectations, and past experiences of exclusion. Additionally, there were varying levels of engagement and openness to new collaborations, with some actors hesitant due to previous difficulties in aligning efforts across organizations. For example, the Royal Danish Academy, which initially collaborated on the organization of a throwing competition during Craft Week 2024, decided to withdraw from this activity for Craft Week 2025 due to the additional workload it entailed. In response, alternative forms of collaboration have been explored, and the Academy has expressed interest in contributing by potentially providing space for the recording of the upcoming podcast series (a HGLL activity, see Section 4.2)—an opportunity that aligns more closely with their current capacity and resources.

A former project manager at BOFA, who also held a coordinating role within the Maker's Island network, provided valuable insights into the landscape of stakeholder perspectives. Drawing on experience from both municipal and craft-sector initiatives, they helped illuminate key opportunities for collaboration as well as underlying tensions within the network. This informed HEPHAESTUS' ability to proactively address emerging concerns and cultivate a more balanced, trust-oriented approach to stakeholder engagement. Some of these challenges are further detailed in Section 4.5.

3.2 Co-Creation Activities

Co-creation activities within HEPHAESTUS are central to the Living Lab methodology (as outlined in Section 2.2), fostering collaboration between researchers, craft practitioners, policymakers, and other stakeholders. These activities provide a structured yet adaptable framework for knowledge exchange, experimentation, and innovation, enabling the development of locally grounded, potentially scalable solutions to pressing challenges in the craft sector — including sustainable material use, digital transitions, and circular economy integration.

Rooted in the values and working principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB)—sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion—these co-creation activities translate the NEB Toolbox's emphasis on participatory design, place-based innovation, and transdisciplinary collaboration into action (European Commission, 2023). They respond to the needs identified in Section 2.2 by operationalizing Living Lab principles such as realism, iteration, and stakeholder engagement (Femmer et al., 2019), making co-creation a practical vehicle for aligning craft-based experimentation with broader EU goals.

These solutions are not abstract: they are iteratively developed, tested, and refined within the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL), where real-world challenges are addressed through participatory design, experimentation, and shared evaluation. This ensures that solutions emerging from the HGLL are context-sensitive while holding relevance for replication across other European craft ecosystems.

Building upon the Craft Network outlined in Section 3.1, these activities have taken shape through workshops, symposia, and collaborative research initiatives. Each engagement supports the interplay between traditional craft knowledge and future-oriented practices, guided by the NEB-aligned and Living Lab-informed frameworks introduced earlier in the report.

The following subsections outline key co-creation events and initiatives that significantly contributed to the establishment and evolution of the HGLL. Figure 5 visualizes this developmental timeline.

LIVING LAB TIMELINE

Figure 5: Timeline of HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab

3.2.1 HEPHAESTUS Symposium at Dals Långed, Sweden (May 2024)

Living Lab Workshop at HEPHAESTUS Itinerant Symposium

At the conclusion of the HEPHAESTUS Itinerant Symposium, held between Gothenburg and Dals Långed, from May 2nd to 5th 2024, BOFA organized and facilitated a collective discussion in the form of a workshop aimed at identifying the perceived challenges, controversies, and tensions in the craft sector within the four ecosystems and to begin outlining possible solutions to address them. This workshop saw the participation of several consortium partners – Copenhagen Business School, Gothenburg University, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, University of Rome Tor Vergata, FabLab Venice, BOFA – as well as representatives from municipalities, local stakeholders, and the craft ambassadors from the four ecosystems of Bassano del Grappa, Bornholm, Dals Långed, and Venice, whose presence ensured the inclusion of diverse and complementary perspectives. The workshop took place in Dals Långed, at Campus Steneby (see Figure 6), a central institution for craft education affiliated with Gothenburg University.

Figure 6: Campus Steneby (HDK-Valand, 2024).

Figure 7: The workshop at Campus Steneby, Dals Långed. Own image

The workshop (see Figure 7) was structured following design thinking principles (Brown, 2009). The participants were divided into three heterogeneous and thematic groups. Specifically, each group focused its discussion on a particular aspect of sustainability: social and cultural sustainability; economic sustainability; environmental sustainability. To ensure diversity – both in terms of regional and professional backgrounds – each group was composed of researchers, craft makers from the different ecosystems, BOFA representatives, and local stakeholders. Initially, each group worked to gather relevant proposals and experiences regarding their respective themes. These experiences, shared and discussed, were then organized based on their relevance and feasibility within the context of the HEPHAESTUS project, and in particular in relation to what was presented during the workshop's introduction by BOFA regarding Bornholm and the establishment and implementation of

the HGLL. Finally, the groups reconvened in a plenary session to present the outcomes of their discussions:

- (iii) *Social and Cultural Sustainability*: The discussion on social and cultural sustainability highlighted the seasonal imbalances in the craft sector, both in terms of natural and tourist cycles. Proposed solutions included promoting diverse activities—such as exhibitions, festivals, and cultural events—during low seasons. Additionally, there was a call for a shared space, both physical and digital, where craft makers from different ecosystems could connect. This would serve not only as a forum for professional exchange and discussion but also as a hub for sharing materials and tools. The shared space would also serve as a hub connecting various craft ecosystem actors—such as universities, local businesses, and the municipality—who could act as facilitators, contributing expertise and resources to support the craft sector.
- (iii) *Economic Sustainability*: In terms of economic sustainability, while one challenge is to prolong the tourist season and develop additional sales channels for craft products, another lies in the identification and design of sustainable business models for craft (see D1.2). A relevant insight was shared by an actor from the Dals Långed ecosystem, highlighting that funding for craft may be more accessible through regional development grants rather than grants traditionally aimed at cultural or artistic activities. In this framing, the craft sector is positioned as a strategic driver of regional development (Jones et al., 2021), capable of attracting skilled professionals and highly educated individuals while advancing circular economy goals. This perspective reflects a broader structural and policy-level approach rather than a Living Lab activity per se, and is further developed in the more think tank-oriented work elaborated in D5.4. It suggests that while such funding dynamics may not be prototyped within the HGLL directly, they nonetheless inform the project's understanding of how craft ecosystems can be supported at a systemic level.
- (iii) *Environmental Sustainability*: The discussion on environmental sustainability began with defining its scope—what it entails, for whom, and who is responsible for creating it. A key focus was the nature of waste, exploring whether sustainability should address the waste generated by craft makers for potential reuse or whether craft makers themselves could serve as a medium for processing certain types of waste. The discussion emphasized the symbiotic relationship between craft making and material reuse, highlighting key challenges such as intellectual property rights, royalties, and the recyclability of different types of waste—especially concerns about toxicity embedded in certain materials. Insights emerged on managing these issues through technical solutions offered by organizations like BOFA. Additionally, the conversation framed creative thinking as an essential act, positioning craft makers as bridges between different fields and ideas. The group emphasized the need to raise awareness of environmental issues and explored ways to engage tourists, citizens, and the broader community. One notable idea was to provide tourists with a set of sustainability guidelines upon arrival, presented in the form of a crafted object. Discussions also touched on ongoing experiments with material recycling through a crushing machine suitable for ceramic waste and highlighted the importance of involving policymakers. Increasing awareness of how these machines function could prompt critical reflections on funding responsibilities, as decisions on how to address these demands are inherently political and should be communicated at both national and European levels.

The workshop at Campus Steneby in Dals Långed organized by BOFA brought together a diverse group of researchers, municipalities representatives, craft makers and relevant stakeholders of the ecosystem to address the multifaceted challenges within the craft sector. By leveraging design thinking principles, the participants were able to collaboratively start to underline key issues and reflect on innovative solutions across social and cultural, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainability. The collaborative efforts during the workshop produced ideas, inspirations, and insights that constituted the first contribution to the design, development and implementation of the HGLL in Bornholm (see Figure 7). The results of the discussions held in Dals Långed, thus, informed and oriented the activities during the following co-creation activities in August 2024, September 2024 and November 2024.

3.2.2 BOFA Resource Day at Bornholm, Denmark (August 2024)

BOFA Resource Day took place at BOFA's facilities, where BOFA personnel David, Dorthe, and the rest of BOFA's project team showcased several Horizon and other sustainability-related projects underway. These initiatives included urban biowaste and wastewater symbiosis efforts in Bornholm using novel biogas technology, and improved collection and citizen communication efforts to improve overall textile waste management on the island. The event was open to the public and attracted approximately 100 attendees from various areas of Bornholm. Visitors had the opportunity to tour BOFA's waste management facilities, including the waste incineration plant for non-recyclable waste, and explore different stands featuring images and explanations of the ongoing projects (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: BOFA Resource Day stands (stand featuring HEPHAESTUS and work of craft ambassador Christina Shou and Brave New World bottom-right). Own images.

HEPHAESTUS contributed to the event with two dedicated stands (see Figure 8). The first stand featured the *D20 exhibition of Brave New World*, displaying AI-generated images and an alternative historic timeline based on craft work. The second stand showcased the work of craft ambassador Christina Shou, who presented ceramic plates glazed with a unique glaze she developed using crushed glass waste. The event brought together a part of the HEPHAESTUS CBS Consortium, including Marta, Marius, Priya, Andrea, Margot, Enrico, BOFA's team Dorthe, Mathias, David; and several attendees from Italy such Sergio, Rafaella.

The primary objective of the activity was to showcase BOFA and HEPHAESTUS ongoing projects to the general public and foster a dynamic exchange of information and knowledge. This occurred primarily through informal discussions between civil servants at BOFA and the public. Though not systematically collected, the attendees, primarily residents of Bornholm, had the opportunity to gain a better understanding of the sustainable solutions BOFA is supporting, as well as its role in the future waste management of Bornholm, alongside HEPHAESTUS' contributions. This event also served as a platform to highlight several ongoing projects, such as: FREIIA (Interreg North Sea), which strengthens island governance through community engagement in circular economy practices; RELOOPED (Interreg South Baltic), which tests sustainable food packaging solutions on Bornholm; One Textile Direction (Innovation Fund Denmark), an initiative focused on creating a sustainable, circular textile industry through collection, sorting, and recycling system; SYMSITES (Horizon Europe) which promotes industrial-urban symbiosis by repurposing wastewater and food

waste for agriculture and biogas production; CEBW (LIFE-Integrated), which targets waste prevention and recycling; and REDOL (Horizon Europe), which develops scalable CE models across different value chains. The breadth of BOFA's activities and the testing aspect of the projects were praised by some members of the public, although BOFA is generally viewed by the public as primarily an organization managing waste collection schemes and waste treatment, and attention was centered on these aspects of BOFA's operations.

This event provided HEPHAESTUS with an opportunity to showcase how BOFA is embedded in it with the HGLL. It highlighted how waste materials can be repurposed for craft production. Christina Shou demonstrated the application of her crushing machine to process food-safe glass waste, such as jam jars, which she then incorporated into ceramic glazes (see Figure 9). By presenting these advancements, HEPHAESTUS and BOFA demonstrated the potential that waste materials bring to craft practices and contributed to the broader discourse on innovative waste management. Through informal discussions, some members of the public showed curiosity about Christina's, BOFA's and HEPHAESTUS' work.

Figure 9: Zoom-In on the stand featuring HEPHAESTUS and work of craft ambassador Christina Schou and Brave New World. Own images.

3.2.3 Focus Group Workshop at Bornholm, Denmark (September 2024)

On September 26th, 2024, a co-creation workshop on sustainability and craft was led by UNITOV with the participation of UNIVE, CBS, and UNIGOT. The co-creation workshop aimed at discussing and better understanding the different layers of sustainability in craft practice, meaning environmental, economic, and social sustainability. This activity is part of Task 4.2 and, more generally, of WP4, oriented towards the development of innovative teaching and learning methods. In particular, our bottom-up approach involves engaging craft-makers and stakeholders as living sources of useful solutions for other craft-makers. For this reason, the workshops on Bornholm, focused on different forms of sustainability (economic, environmental, and social), various aspects of which revealed themselves to be topical for craft-makers in the co-creation process, both as topics that fostered discussions among each other and with the researchers of HEPHAESTUS.

At the same time, in the spirit of collaboration among research teams, which is one of the guiding principles of HEPHAESTUS, this activity also feeds into WP5, and in particular Tasks 5.2 and 5.4:

Indeed, the co-creation workshop contributed to the development of the HGLL by serving as a pilot activity for testing collaboration between different HEPHAESTUS partners and the local community of craft makers. Such co-creation with diverse craft practitioners is a core component of the HGLL approach. Participants in the co-creation included scholars from Tor Vergata University, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, the University of Gothenburg, and CBS, alongside craft makers, craft ambassadors from Bornholm, and BOFA members. This in-person engagement enabled direct, trust-building dialogue and collaborative exploration of local challenges, which proved especially valuable in strengthening connections between BOFA and the craft maker community—connections that are often harder to cultivate in digital settings. The co-creation workshop also relates to Task 5.4: report on the vision think tank, focusing on sustainability and circular economy. Indeed, the workshop explored the themes of social, environmental, and economic sustainability in relation to craft practice, fostering dialogue and a participatory exchange between BOFA and local craft makers. While the circular economy was introduced as a relevant framework – particularly in the Bornholm context – participants reflected on the complexity of applying such models directly within their own practices. Rather than focusing on specific material reuse strategies, the discussion highlighted broader interpretations of sustainability, including questions of identity, time, seasonal rhythms, and the difficulty of aligning personal values with market demands. These reflections provided valuable insights into how sustainability is understood and negotiated in craft practice, offering perspectives that are relevant not only to Bornholm, but also to the wider ecosystems within HEPHAESTUS.

The co-creation started with an initial presentation of the results of the questionnaire on craft skills (see D4.1) in order to discuss them with local craft makers and acknowledge differences in terms of education and skills (1h). This first part aimed also at testing our understanding of the data gathered, i.e. validating the questionnaire data, while also creating a safe discussion environment to add critique and provide nuances to the results. The second part of the co-creation (2h) was organized as a focus group, with participants sitting in circle and debating on issues proposed by UNITOV, the participants were 20 circa (see Figure 10). The discussion was centred around two dimensions of sustainability: economic and environmental.

Figure 10: The second part of the co-creation workshop. Own image.

Economic Sustainability

Bornholm's economy, driven largely by seasonal tourism, presents a challenge for local craft makers. The peak tourist season during the summer provides an essential source of income (roughly 700,000 tourists during May-September on an island of 40,000 inhabitants), but the remainder of the year is marked by financial uncertainty. Participants noted that it was difficult to rely on seasonal income alone, leading many to take on secondary jobs during the off-season to make ends meet, often completely unrelated to craft. One participant described how they juggled part-time work alongside their craft practice, emphasizing that while the tourist season offered a financial boost, it was not enough to sustain them year-round. This constant pressure to sustain a livelihood outside the craft-making season underscores the precarious nature of relying on tourism alone. A craft maker also suggested producing different lines of products, one more dedicated to tourists and another one more big-scale or artistic, as this, in the long term, permitted her to self-sustain with her craft activity.

Many craft makers expressed frustrations over the lack of financial support available to small-scale artisans. The focus group participants emphasized the need for more accessible financial support, particularly in the form of micro-grants or subsidies tailored to the specific needs of craft makers.

Environmental Sustainability

In the co-creation workshop, craft makers on Bornholm expressed concerns about the environmental impact of their work. This aligns with previous studies, where it has been noted that craft makers on Bornholm have actively engaged with the environmental implications of their work, not only expressing concern over material use and waste, but also participating in formal sustainability-focused capacity-building initiatives (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2024). These efforts reflect a growing awareness within the local craft sector that environmental responsibility is integral to both their professional practice and regional identity.

The dilemma arises from the fact that while they aim to be environmentally conscious, the very nature of producing physical objects can feel contradictory to the principles of sustainability. Some craft makers described a tension between their personal environmental values and broader sustainability narratives. For instance, sustainability was often equated with "common sense" practices—such as not wasting materials or repurposing leftovers—rather than with formal certifications or policies. At the same time, several participants expressed skepticism toward how sustainability is promoted in mainstream discourse, describing it as a "label" sometimes used by large companies or affluent consumers as part of greenwashing strategies. While not opposing the idea of sustainability itself, these reflections pointed to a desire for more authentic, practice-based approaches rooted in craft values and material sensitivity. However, the relationship between sustainability and bigger companies can also be a positive one, where craft makers provide creative and innovative ideas on sustainable practices to be endorsed by big companies, acting as a sort of innovative hubs or start-ups. Participants discussed the challenges of sourcing sustainable materials, particularly when many resources have to be imported due to the island's lack of local raw materials. Craft makers often reuse materials and minimize waste, but the broader environmental footprint of imported resources still poses a significant challenge. Many expressed a sense of guilt over the environmental consequences of their work, even though they practiced sustainability in smaller, everyday ways, such as repurposing leftover materials or reusing clay. Despite these challenges, the participants highlighted numerous innovative ways they were incorporating sustainability into their work. Several artisans described how they reused materials, such as recycling clay. Participants also discussed the potential for more collaboration between craft makers and other sectors to foster sustainability. The idea of creating a "materials bank" was raised, where artisans could access second-hand or waste materials for reuse in their projects. Participants felt that a stronger network of collaboration, perhaps supported by local government or institutions, could help scale up these efforts.

A key takeaway from the co-creation workshop was that while many craft makers expressed skepticism toward externally imposed sustainability agendas—particularly those focused on waste reuse—this resistance often softened when practices aligned with their own creative goals or values. In such cases, sustainability became a driver of innovation rather than a constraint. The workshop also revealed that sustainability in craft practice is not limited to environmental concerns but is deeply entangled with economic viability and social dynamics—such as seasonality, community engagement, and identity. This suggests that any meaningful sustainability framework for the craft sector must be flexible, value-sensitive, and responsive to the lived realities of makers.

3.2.4 Living Lab Workshop on Bornholm, Denmark (November 2024)

As part of the implementation phase of the HGLL, a two-day workshop was held on Bornholm on November 26th to 27th, 2024, organized by BOFA in collaboration with Copenhagen Business School. The primary objective of the workshop was to finalize the establishment of the HGLL on Bornholm, holding discussions structured around four core thematic areas: 1) the conceptual framework of the HGLL, 2) Sustainable business models, 3) synergies across the different WPs, 4) Planning the launch event and formalizing the framework.

The first area of focus was the conceptual framework of the HGLL, which served as a preparatory step for D5.2. This session aimed to refine the theoretical underpinnings of the HGLL, ensuring that its methodological approach aligns with the broader objectives of the project.

The second key topic addressed the development of sustainable business models (relating to WP1 and Task 1.3) and strategies to strengthen the support network for craft makers on Bornholm, particularly through the integration of circular economy principles. A specific challenge within this discussion was the management of ceramic waste, specifically discarded toilets and sinks, which are prevalent on the island. Participants examined potential solutions by taking into consideration the necessity of knowing the properties of the crushed ceramic materials, estimating the volume of waste generated, and identifying the machinery required to process these materials for reuse by craft makers. Furthermore, the discussion focused on the feasibility of establishing a sustainable approach to working with these materials, as well as the possible products that could be created from repurposed ceramics and their potential applications – eventually this has led to one of the ongoing activities in the HGLL described in Section 4.

The third major theme of the workshop centered on the synergies between the different work packages (WPs) within the project. This session aimed to identify the interconnections between the activities that contributed to the establishment of the HGLL and to ensure that these activities align with the overarching goals of HEPHAESTUS. A visualization of the different WPs and their contributions and connection to the HGLL can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Output of Living Lab Workshop Bornholm: Interaction between WP5 and WPs

The fourth component of the workshop was dedicated to planning the official launch of the HGLL, scheduled for March 2025. This discussion outlined the objectives and expected outcomes of the event, which is further outlined in section 4.1. In addition to these structured discussions, a critical aspect of the workshop was the development of a shared understanding of the HGLL's structure and operational framework. A collaborative brainstorming session led to the creation of a visualization of the HGLL as a 'nexus' illustrating the interconnected network of stakeholders on Bornholm who contribute to its implementation (see Figure 12). This exercise facilitated a clearer articulation of the roles and relationships that underpin the HGLL's ecosystem. Moreover, the workshop resulted in the formalization of the HGLL's timeline and highlighting of its three foundational pillars: economic, social, and environmental sustainability. By establishing these key parameters, the

workshop provided a structured pathway for the continued development and long-term sustainability of the HGLL.

Bornholm’s Stakeholder Map

Figure 12: Bornholm’s Stakeholder Map

4. Implementation of the HEPHAESTUS GREEN Living Lab

This section outlines the implementation phase of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL), translating co-created ideas into real-world activities. Building on the co-creation events and Living Lab principles described earlier—particularly the emphasis on participation, sustainability, and place-based innovation—the activities described here exemplify how abstract ideas were tested, adapted, and operationalized through concrete projects on Bornholm.

Each initiative engages diverse stakeholders, from craft makers and municipal actors to researchers and the public. Together, they form the active backbone of the HGLL, showcasing how cross-sector collaboration can generate sustainable, aesthetically grounded, and inclusive practices—reflecting the values of the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

The following subsections detail flagship initiatives launched under the HGLL, including artistic experimentation, community engagement, infrastructure adaptation, and new forms of knowledge sharing. While some projects are already underway, others remain in the planning or prototyping stage, collectively demonstrating the evolving, iterative nature of the Living Lab approach.

4.1 Launch Event - Opening at Oficinet

Green Living Lab (HGLL) (see Figure 13). Situated in central Copenhagen and directly next to the Danish Design Museum, Oficinet is a distinguished exhibition space for contemporary craft and design, providing a highly relevant platform to communicate the ambitions of the HEPHAESTUS Project and reach a wider public audience. *Ødeland*, meaning “Wasteland,” is the outcome of a collaborative project between ceramic artists Christina Schou Christensen, Signe Fensholt, and Thora Finnsdottir. The exhibition explores the aesthetic and functional potential of ceramic waste—tiles, bricks, toilets, and melted glass—transformed into sculptural and decorative objects. Drawing on both individual and joint works, the three artists demonstrate the possibilities of reusing discarded materials in ways that challenge conventional approaches to design, while promoting resource conservation and material circularity.

The gallery was completely full with attendees and standing-room only during speeches. Traversing around the gallery became precarious for those with large jackets or bags for fear of damaging the ceramic works, resulting in the right side of the atelier becoming a makeshift “coatroom” for the diverse and conscientious crowd. The success of the exhibition is highlighted in the tight and narrow spaces one had to gently push through in order to view the three long exhibition tables—each requiring several minutes to fully explore. The exhibition incorporated QR codes linking to the official website www.oedeland.dk, where visitors could learn more about the artistic process, the materials used and their recipes, and the project’s connection to Bornholm’s circular economy efforts. These QR codes also linked to a price scheme, reflecting an experimental attempt to connect sustainable material reuse with viable business models. While no formal sales records were available at the time of writing, several pieces are believed to have been sold during or after the exhibition, introducing an economic dimension to the event and suggesting potential pathways for sustainable, waste-based craft practices to enter the market.

Figure 13: The Opening of “Ødeland” at Oficinet. Own images.

The project is rooted in the paradox between the perceived scarcity of natural raw materials, such as clay and minerals, and the abundance of post-consumer ceramic waste—a paradox increasingly recognized in Bornholm’s craft sector, where concerns about sustainable material sourcing intersect with growing awareness of underutilized waste streams (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2024). On Bornholm, BOFA has recorded a significant and consistent intake of porcelain sanitation waste over the past three years. In 2022, the total amounted to 22,460 kg, followed by an increase to 31,070 kg in 2023. In early 2024, 1,140 kg had already been collected, underlining the continued relevance of identifying sustainable reuse pathways for these materials within the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (BOFA, 2024). The artists’ practices embrace this tension by rethinking how value can be derived from what is typically discarded. The resulting pieces form a tactile and visual library of waste-based techniques, revealing new opportunities for sustainability in craft.

Ødeland was developed in close collaboration with BOFA (Bornholm’s municipal waste authority), aligning with Bornholm’s “Zero Waste” vision (BOFA, 2019) and contributing to the broader green transition. The exhibition emphasized not only small-scale, studio-based reuse but also the potential for upscaling these methods to industrial processes. The partnership with BOFA underlined the systemic relevance of the work and its implications for waste management policy and practice.

The launch event brought together key HEPHAESTUS partners, including Copenhagen Business School (CBS) and BOFA, and featured an opening speech by Anne-Louise Sommer, Director of Designmuseum Danmark. The event catalyzed interdisciplinary dialogue around sustainability, design innovation, and cross-sector collaboration.

Acclaimed for its balance of pedagogy and aesthetic expression, the exhibition successfully communicated complex environmental issues through accessible and tangible formats. By sharing their methods and findings on the platform www.oedeland.dk, and publication of the opening materials, program, and website in both Danish and English languages, the artists further extended the exhibition’s reach, encouraging broader experimentation with ceramic reuse across the craft and design sectors.

In this way, the *Ødeland* exhibition served not only as the launch of the HGLL but also as a compelling demonstration of how artistic practice can intersect with environmental innovation and public engagement. It embodies the working principles of the Living Lab as introduced in Section 2.2—particularly its role as a real-world testbed for co-creation, experimentation, and circular

innovation at the intersection of materials, aesthetics, and systems change (European Commission, 2024; Femmer et al., 2019). Appendix 1 shows the press release of the launch event and the exhibition, including the website and other materials.

4.2 Ongoing Living Lab Activities

This section presents the ongoing HGLL activities, emphasizing their focus on co-creation and stakeholder engagement. It highlights how these activities ensure that craft makers are involved from the initial stages of exploration and problematization, helping the research team define challenges and refine potential solutions. These solutions are then tested within the HGLL and now take shape as the activities outlined below. These activities contribute to long-term sustainability, support the replicability of the HGLL in other contexts, and represent the essential network of actors that underpin the HGLL on Bornholm.

The ongoing HGLL activities build on insights from the HEPHAESTUS Symposium and co-creation workshops in Bornholm, translating key discussions on sustainability into action. Rooted in NEB principles of co-creation and circularity, these activities strengthen networks, foster cross-sector collaboration, and support policy engagement. By integrating craft makers from the start, the HGLL ensures that solutions are both practical and innovative, reinforcing Bornholm’s role as a ‘test island’ for sustainable transitions. It is possible to see the ongoing Living Lab activities in Figure 14.

Current Research & Activities

Figure 14: Ongoing Living Lab Activities overview

4.2.1 Ødeland Crushing Machine Project – Christina Schou Christensen

Christina Schou Christensen, a prominent advocate for Bornholm’s craft ecosystem, is exploring the potential for recycling porcelain waste, including discarded toilets and sinks, through the use of a specialized crushing machine. In collaboration with ceramicists Thora Finnsdottir and Signe Fensholt, she has initiated a partnership with BOFA to facilitate proper waste sorting, material handling, and compliance with pertinent EU directives.

A particularly relevant aspect of this initiative is its intersection of technology, sustainability, and innovation within the craft sector. Christina’s integration of the crushing machine to produce experimental glazes from waste materials exemplifies how craft businesses can adopt new technologies to create sustainable products. This aligns with broader efforts to explore new municipal business models for porcelain waste management.

To ensure regulatory compliance, BOFA has commissioned an elemental analysis from Eurofins VBM Laboratoriet, particularly concerning lead and cadmium content (see Figure 15), with strict detection thresholds for occupational safety and final product quality. Additionally, BOFA is conducting research on various toilet and sink manufacturers to identify materials most suitable for further ceramic testing.

Lab prøvenr:	862-2025-00745606	862-2025-00745607	862-2025-00745608	862-2025-00745609	Enhed	DL	Urel(%)
Prøvemærke:	107.8 - 2476529	108.0 - 2476514	109.6 - 2476534	107.5 - 2476530			
Metaller							
Arsen (As) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 2	< 2	< 2	< 2	mg/kg	2	30
Bly (Pb) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 2	< 2	< 2	< 2	mg/kg	2	30
Cadmium (Cd) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	mg/kg	0,05	30
Chrom (Cr) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 1	< 1	< 1	140	mg/kg	1	30
Kobber (Cu) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 2	< 2	< 2	< 2	mg/kg	2	30
Kviksølv (Hg) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15175-1:2016 mod. CV-AAS</small>	< 0,01	< 0,01	< 0,01	< 0,01	mg/kg	0,01	30
Nikkel (Ni) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	< 1	< 1	< 1	1,8	mg/kg	1	30
Zink (Zn) <small>DS 259:2003, DSI/EN 15170:2016 mod. ICP-OES</small>	15	11	3,0	15	mg/kg	2	30

Figure 15: Excerpt from crushed ceramic waste material powder analysis report (Eurofins VBM Laboratoriet, 2025).

This collaboration integrates the creative expertise and material knowledge of craft makers with BOFA’s regulatory and infrastructural resources, forming a cornerstone of the HGLL’s applied experimentation. By engaging directly with real-world waste streams and testing material reuse through ceramic innovation, the project exemplifies the Living Lab principle of realism, while also reflecting co-creation through its cross-sectoral approach. It contributes to HEPHAESTUS objectives by advancing circular craft practices, prototyping sustainable material systems, and informing new business models that align with EU regulatory frameworks. As such, the Ødeland Crushing Machine Project not only supports the adaptive transformation of the craft sector on Bornholm, but also strengthens the replicability of the Living Lab approach across other ecosystems.

4.2.2 Kiln with Waste Oil Firing

Sara Jeffries, a craft ambassador in Bornholm’s ecosystem, has proposed the development of a ceramic kiln powered by waste cooking oil sourced from local restaurants. This alternative energy concept seeks to reduce dependence on conventional fuels such as wood or gas, and aligns with broader sustainability goals in both the ceramic and food service sectors. The initiative is being developed in collaboration with BOFA, which already maintains partnerships with restaurants that currently pay for the disposal of used fryer oil—presenting a clear opportunity to redirect this waste stream into a valuable resource for local craft production.

The project remains in its early stages. Initial outreach has included exploratory dialogues with students and faculty from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and Copenhagen Business School (CBS), with the aim of identifying co-development opportunities across engineering, sustainability, and business model design. While significant technical challenges persist—particularly concerning CO₂ emissions and whether additional filtration or combustion control technologies are required—the project has catalyzed a knowledge-sharing process across sectors and institutions.

At its core, the kiln initiative is a testbed for low-carbon craft infrastructure: combining waste recovery, energy innovation, and ceramic traditions in a single system. It offers a compelling use case for rethinking how small-scale craft production can intersect with resource circularity and local material loops.

This activity directly contributes to the goals of the HEPHAESTUS project by fostering innovation in sustainable craft infrastructure and supporting cross-sector collaboration. It exemplifies key principles of the Living Lab framework—especially co-creation, realism, and experimentation—by engaging multiple stakeholders in the early conceptualization of a real-world system. As it evolves, the project has the potential to strengthen the HGLL’s role as a site for ecological transitions rooted in place-based craft practice.

4.2.3 Podcast “Bornholm’s Craft Knowledge: A Digital Oral and Audio Narrative”

In addition to the overarching *Podcraft* podcast series developed under the HEPHAESTUS project umbrella, a localized podcast is being co-created as part of the Bornholm-based HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). While *Podcraft* explores cross-cutting themes relevant to all four project ecosystems—Denmark, Sweden, and Italy—with episodes available in multiple languages (see [Podcraft series overview](#) and [English version](#)), this new podcast focuses specifically on the voices, concerns, and knowledge of Bornholm’s craft makers. It aims to amplify local narratives while supporting the co-creation of content tailored to regional sustainability challenges and opportunities.

The need for such a shared digital storytelling platform emerged clearly during the *social and cultural sustainability* discussion at the Dals Långed Symposium (see Section 3.2.1), where participants emphasized the importance of accessible spaces—both physical and digital—for makers to connect across geographies and share experiences. This podcast responds directly to that call, offering a place-based medium for dialogue, professional identity-building, and long-term knowledge preservation.

To initiate participation, an open call was shared through the Arts and Crafts Association of Bornholm (ACAB) Facebook group (see Figure 16), inviting local craft makers to contribute to shaping the project. On March 31, 2025—the day of this report’s submission—a hybrid planning meeting was held with six craft makers (five in-person and one online, see Figure 18), alongside project team members. Together, they co-developed the conceptual structure of the podcast series, including its thematic scope (8–10 episodes), potential audiences, preferred formats, and dissemination channels. The session was lively, reflective, and future-focused. Participants expressed genuine ownership of the podcast initiative and clear excitement for its next phase, scheduled to begin in May 2025.

Figure 16: The podcast Facebook group page.

Tentative Themes

-
1. **"Why did you move here?"**
Aside from the obvious answers like the beautiful nature and friendly atmosphere & people, we share our real honest experiences. Why did you move here and why do you stay?
 2. **"Sustainable Art?"**
Critical view on how sustainability is abused in the creative industry. Dilemmas in fundraising and open call requirements.
 3. **"Artist? Designer? Or craftsmen? Which one are you?"**
What are the differences and why are we obsessed?
 4. **"Luxurious life of a poor artist"**
What it's like to be a poor, not so young anymore, professional artist.
 5. **"Influencer ceramicist"**
Is it annoying to see unskilled, hobby artists selling out? What does it mean?
 6. **"AI generated art"**
How receptive are you towards technology? Is it your friend or enemy?
 7. **"Tourism Craft"**
Who is offering what to whom, and who benefits?
 8. **"Highlight"**
Last episode of season 1.
What are some of the most impressive highlights of your career and what is your dream exhibition?
-

Figure 17: Tentative podcast themes. Own elaboration.

A tentative list of episode themes (see Figure 17) was presented and critiqued, and what emerged was a specified and localized collaborative planning process, covering topics such as *AI-generated art*, *tourism and craft*, *identity and professionalization*, *sustainability narratives*, and *influencer culture* in the ceramic field. These themes reflect not only the diversity of practices represented within the Bornholm craft community, but also the complexity of navigating sustainability, visibility, and tradition as creative professionals.

This initiative also echoes the findings of Zumach and Portillo (2020), who describe podcasting as a powerful tool for cultivating communities of practice—enabling dialogic exchange and shared identity formation across distributed groups. In this context, the Bornholm podcast becomes not just a content platform, but a relational infrastructure for reflection, learning, and cross-sector dialogue.

Supporting the Living Lab principles of openness, influence, and co-creation, the podcast directly contributes to the HEPHAESTUS objectives by piloting new models for place-based communication, strengthening the regional craft network, and providing a replicable format for digital storytelling. It aligns closely with WP4, particularly Task 4.2, and benefits from the pedagogical and methodological expertise of CBS and Tor Vergata. Together, the Bornholm podcast and the broader *Podcraft* ecosystem exemplify how digital media can serve as tools for cultural mediation and collaborative sustainability learning.

Figure 18: Podcast co-creation meeting. Own image.

4.2.4 Recreational Sculpture Using Waste Bricks

This initiative critically engages with Bornholm’s current waste handling practices, focusing on the export of whole brick waste to the private company *Gamle Mursten* in Svendborg. While *Gamle Mursten* offers a well-established model for brick reuse, this project explores the potential for a more localized, craft-driven approach that supports community engagement and circular material flows on the island itself. Rather than discarding or outsourcing reuse processes, the initiative calls for shared responsibility and innovative, site-specific solutions.

At its core, the project seeks to activate public space through recreational sculpture constructed from locally sourced waste bricks. By integrating artistic craftsmanship, spatial design, and environmental concern, it serves as both a creative intervention and a platform for public discourse. The sculptural elements are intended not only to showcase material reuse but also to foster dialogue about sustainability, land use, and collective ownership of waste challenges.

The project's success relies on collaboration between craft makers, designers, and municipal authorities. Technical expertise and aesthetic considerations must align with logistical factors, including land-use permissions, material storage, and long-term maintenance. As of this writing, the project team is actively seeking municipal approval for a proposed site, with initial inquiries submitted to local planning authorities. Securing this location would unlock opportunities for collaborative fundraising, cross-sectoral partnerships, and public programming linked to the installation.

Bricks – a recyclable construction materials capable of retaining structural integrity – require a high degree of skill in both deconstruction and reassembly. This characteristic ties directly to the principles of circular craft innovation, where material constraints become a catalyst for design, problem-solving, and social engagement.

This initiative exemplifies the Living Lab principle of realism by tackling a real-world material challenge in a specific geographical and institutional setting. It supports co-creation by involving diverse stakeholders—from craft makers and municipal planners to waste managers and community members—and emphasizes inclusivity by situating artistic practice within public space.

In line with HEPHAESTUS objectives, the project builds capacity for sustainable craft experimentation, nurtures new collaborative governance models, and reinforces the role of artistic practice in advancing green transition goals. By reimagining waste as a cultural resource, the initiative contributes to the adaptive transformation of Bornholm's craft ecosystem, while offering a replicable example of how material reuse and community engagement can intersect through Living Lab methodology.

4.2.5 Slow Tourism Initiatives

Bornholm's craft sector plays a pivotal role in shaping the island's tourism identity, offering experiences that are both culturally rooted and economically significant. Recognizing this influence, the Slow Tourism Initiatives seek to develop new collaborations between craft makers and local stakeholders—such as hotels, restaurants, museums, and tour operators—to co-create more sustainable, place-sensitive forms of tourism.

These efforts are currently in the ideation phase, where potential partnerships are being mapped, and project concepts explored through early-stage dialogue. The aim is to shift away from volume-driven tourism models and toward experiences that foster deeper visitor engagement with Bornholm's cultural heritage, craft knowledge, and environmental stewardship. This includes developing slower, more intentional encounters with the island's landscape and traditions, in which craft becomes not just a product, but a gateway to understanding local values.

By leveraging Bornholm's unique characteristics as a geographically bounded, community-oriented environment, the initiative cultivates a sense of shared responsibility among residents, visitors, and creative professionals. These early explorations also create opportunities for participatory tourism design—where craft makers help define what meaningful, sustainable tourism looks like in their local context.

This initiative aligns with the Living Lab framework as a space of co-creation, realism, and experimentation. Although not yet implemented, the ideation process itself is a core Living Lab activity—inviting multiple actors to explore and prototype sustainable transitions in real-world settings. By prioritizing community-led tourism narratives, the initiative embodies inclusivity and supports place-based innovation through cultural production.

In relation to the broader HEPHAESTUS objectives, the Slow Tourism Initiatives reinforce the role of craft in enabling systemic change. They promote the integration of social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainability by positioning craft makers as key agents in regenerative tourism development. In doing so, the initiative helps expand the HGLL's impact beyond the studio or workshop—embedding it within the broader rhythms and relationships that shape Bornholm's future.

4.2.6 Textile Transformation Workshop

Potentially as part of Craft Weeks 2025, HEPHAESTUS is developing a Textile Transformation Workshop in collaboration with textile artist Ann Charlott Skogøy, whose practice centers on sustainability, aesthetics, and circular material flows. Rather than restoring materials to their original function—as in traditional repair workshops—this initiative focuses on creative transformation, elevating discarded textiles into expressive works of art.

Ann Charlott Skogøy previously contributed to the HEPHAESTUS network in the preparation of the *Plastigma* exhibition in 2024, where she created a series of sculptural pieces using waste plastics. More recently, her work has explored the interplay between natural and synthetic detritus, such as suspended installations made from fallen branches and strips of textile waste—reframing the overlooked as valuable through thoughtful composition and color.

The proposed workshop will invite participants to work hands-on with textile waste sourced from BOFA’s recycling center. Drawing inspiration from the textures, colors, and histories embedded in these materials, participants will co-create original textile artworks that reflect both personal and environmental narratives. In doing so, the workshop invites reflection on the value of waste, the aesthetics of sustainability, and the potential for materials to be transformed rather than discarded.

Initial conversations around logistics include the possibility of hosting the event at a public library venue, in collaboration with local cultural actors who support community engagement and sustainability outreach. By locating the workshop in an accessible, public setting, the project aims to attract a wide audience and strengthen ties between the craft sector and civic institutions.

This workshop represents more than a creative event – it is an exploration of how material transformation can inspire new relationships between people, waste, and environment. By foregrounding reuse and participatory art-making, the initiative supports the Living Lab principles of influence (through public dialogue), co-creation (through hands-on collaboration), and inclusivity (through accessible, community-facing programming).

In alignment with the HEPHAESTUS objectives, the Textile Transformation Workshop contributes to the development of circular craft methodologies, promotes public engagement in sustainability, and expands the Green Living Lab’s reach beyond professional makers to include everyday citizens. By embedding sustainable creativity into a high-visibility cultural event like Craft Weeks, the initiative reinforces Bornholm’s position as a testbed for socially and environmentally grounded craft innovation.

4.2.7 Craft Weeks

Building on the existing annual event organized by Maker’s Island, the HEPHAESTUS Project seeks to inspire Bornholm’s craft makers to take an active role in the green transition. In collaboration with the Maker’s Island Secretariat, HEPHAESTUS is contributing to the development of a sustainability theme for Bornholm’s Craft Weeks 2025. An initial meeting on March 17th 2025, opened discussions on economic coordination, communication strategy, and craft maker engagement. Bi-weekly meetings have since been established to ensure an evolving, participatory planning process.

The initiative begins with an exploration of how craft makers perceive their responsibilities within the green transition. This process aims to cultivate a culture that recognizes and values the professional expertise of craft makers in sustainability—not only environmentally, but also in social and economic dimensions. Practitioners who work directly with physical, often energy-intensive materials have a deep understanding of extraction costs, production consequences, and long-term impacts. Their perspectives offer critical insights into broader environmental challenges and potential pathways for transformation.

As emphasized in recent policy dialogues, creative professionals possess the cultural tools necessary to help societies visualize sustainable futures, question extractive norms, and co-create new environmental imaginaries (Voices of Culture, 2023). In this way, integrating creative perspectives is essential to addressing the complex societal shifts demanded by the green transition.

Rather than serving only as event contributors, craft makers are being positioned as central participants in knowledge exchange, policy dialogue, and co-creation of public programming. The 2025 Craft Weeks will therefore center not on compliance or surface-level “green” branding, but on meaningful, critical engagement with the challenges and potential of sustainable practice.

By connecting craft makers, policymakers, and the public through thematic activities, this initiative advances the HEPHAESTUS Project's objectives of fostering interdisciplinary dialogue, supporting sustainable business models, and creating inclusive platforms for environmental and cultural exchange. It exemplifies the Living Lab (LL) principles of openness, influence, and systemic experimentation by embedding co-created sustainability narratives into a major cultural tradition—ensuring long-term impact and transformation.

4.3 Mapping the Living Lab: Connecting Co-Creation, NEB Principles, and Practice

The ongoing activities of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) are rooted in the co-creation processes described in Section 4. These workshops and focus groups – held across Dals Långed and Bornholm – brought together craft makers, researchers, and local stakeholders to explore sustainability through the lenses of social, environmental, and economic dimensions. The ideas developed through these co-creation sessions informed and inspired the Living Lab initiatives that followed.

Table 1 below illustrates how each HGLL activity aligns with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles—sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion—while also showing how these activities draw from earlier co-creation activities. The third column not only traces the origin of each activity within the project's co-creative dialogue, but also reflects how insights were translated into real-world action. This helps clarify the iterative and participatory nature of the Living Lab framework, emphasizing the role of diverse actors in shaping responsive, place-based innovation.

Living Lab Activity	NEB Principles Addressed	Related Co-Creation Activities
4.2.1 Ødeland Crushing Machine Project – Christina Schou Christensen	Sustainability (material reuse, circular economy), Aesthetics (craft design from recycled materials), Inclusivity (community engagement)	Built on insights from Environmental Sustainability discussions at the May 2024 Symposium in Dals Långed (Section 3.2.1) and September 2024 Focus Group (Section 3.2.3), where reuse of materials and systemic collaboration were identified as strategic priorities.
4.2.2 Kiln with Waste Oil Firing	Sustainability (alternative energy, reducing waste), Aesthetics (maintaining traditional craft techniques), Inclusivity (engaging restaurant and waste sectors)	Emerges from ideas raised during the November 2024 Living Lab Workshop (Section 3.2.4) on sustainable infrastructure and speculative projects. This track also responds to the interest in testing low-carbon craft methods noted across co-creation sessions.
4.2.3 Podcast “Bornholm’s Craft Knowledge: A Digital Oral and Audio Narrative”	Aesthetics (craft narratives and identity), Sustainability (intergenerational knowledge transfer), Inclusivity (public and digital engagement)	Direct response to Social and Cultural Sustainability needs raised at Dals Långed Symposium (Section 3.2.1) — especially the call for shared (digital) spaces. The co-creation workshop in September 2024 (Section 3.2.3) also validated the need for visibility and storytelling tools for craft makers.
4.2.4 Recreational Sculpture Using Waste Bricks	Sustainability (reuse of construction waste), Aesthetics (sculptural interventions in public spaces), Inclusivity (municipal co-development)	Developed through November 2024 Living Lab Workshop (Section 3.2.4), which focused on ideation and testing for public-facing, cross-sector co-creation projects that link waste reuse with public engagement.
4.2.5 Slow Tourism Initiatives	Sustainability (cultural preservation, regenerative tourism), Aesthetics (craft-based visitor experiences), Inclusivity (local stakeholder and tourist collaboration)	Rooted in discussions on economic sustainability and seasonality from the May 2024 Symposium (Section 3.2.1) and September 2024 Focus Group (Section 3.2.3). Developed to extend the value of craft beyond products and into visitor experience design.
4.2.6 Textile Transformation Workshop	Sustainability (upcycling and waste valorization), Aesthetics (experimental textile reuse),	Shaped by the November 2024 Living Lab Workshop (Section 3.2.4), where the reuse of textile

	Inclusivity (community engagement through libraries)	waste and the importance of working with non-traditional venues (e.g. public libraries) emerged as opportunities for creative citizen engagement.
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Table 1: HGLL alignments with New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles

4.4 Visual Identity and representation of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab

A clear and coherent visual identity is essential for communicating the purpose, scope, and collaborative nature of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). It supports public visibility, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with the project's broader sustainability mission.

During the co-creation workshop on Bornholm in September 2024 (see D4.1), participating craft makers expressed a desire to use the Living Lab as a platform not only for refining their professional skills—particularly in business and communication—but also for fostering interdisciplinary collaborations. At the same time, they raised important concerns about the clarity and communicability of the “Living Lab” concept, particularly to wider audiences unfamiliar with the terminology. These insights prompted a re-evaluation of the HGLL’s communication and branding strategy.

Rather than introducing a new, standalone visual identity for the HGLL, the project team decided to adapt and extend the existing HEPHAESTUS project identity. This decision was based on key findings from workshops and ambassador feedback indicating that:

- Many Living Lab activities are developed by individual craft makers or small groups.
- Each of these activities tends to have, or is likely to develop, a distinct visual style.
- Imposing a single, overarching HGLL brand could risk overshadowing or conflicting with these personal and creative identities.

This point was particularly emphasized by artist Christina Schou Christensen, who requested that BOFA not bring printed HEPHAESTUS-branded materials to the Ødeland exhibition opening. Her concern was that BOFA's visual style clashed with the established aesthetic of the exhibition and could confuse the audience. Instead, Ødeland integrated HEPHAESTUS’s presence through its own design language, ensuring coherence and clarity of expression.

To accommodate the plurality of expressions within the HGLL while still maintaining project cohesion, a dedicated landing page was created on the official [HEPHAESTUS website](#). This page introduces the Living Lab concept and presents each activity individually, allowing:

- Each project to retain its unique visual identity.
- A unified representation under the HEPHAESTUS umbrella.
- Viewers to explore Living Lab content without being overwhelmed by conflicting brand signals.

This flexible structure reinforces participants’ sense of ownership while providing a coherent narrative for audiences, partners, and policymakers. Importantly, all activities supported through HEPHAESTUS maintain proper funding attribution—including display of the EU emblem and

required acknowledgements—even when their visual identities differ from the central project branding. A summary of the current visual identity strategy is as follows:

Activity	Visual Identity Approach
Ødeland	Independent identity, strongly protected by lead artists. HEPHAESTUS represented through Ødeland’s visual language.
Podcast	A unique visual identity is being co-created with participating craft makers to reflect Bornholm’s local voices.
Recreational Sculpture, Waste Oil Kiln	Expected to develop their own visual styles reflecting their spatial/public nature.
Craft Weeks	Continues under Maker’s Island’s established branding.
Textile Transformation Workshop	Will be visually framed within the HEPHAESTUS or Craft Weeks identity, not developing a standalone look.
Slow Tourism Initiatives	Will follow the branding of future collaboration partners (e.g., hotels, museums, tourism boards).

Table 2: Activities and Visual Identity Approaches

This modular communication strategy ensures that the Living Lab’s activities remain accessible, legible, and appealing to diverse audiences—without flattening the richness of each creative project. It responds directly to the needs identified in co-creation workshops, reduces potential confusion, and strengthens overall engagement. Most importantly, it reflects the Living Lab principle of inclusivity, by recognizing the distinct voices and visual cultures of the craft makers who are central to its implementation.

Figure 19: HGLL Landing Page and activity subpages (concept visuals).

4.5 Challenges and barriers to implementation

The implementation of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) on Bornholm has revealed a range of challenges that underscore both the complexity and the opportunity inherent in building a Living Lab at the intersection of craft, sustainability, and innovation. These challenges are not signs of failure but rather key learning moments in the iterative development of a robust, inclusive, and place-sensitive experimentation platform (European Commission, 2024; Femmer et al., 2019).

Crucially, the Living Lab's strength lies in its responsiveness to context—something that necessarily brings friction when new methods, stakeholders, and ambitions are layered onto existing systems. As such, the following barriers are best understood not as fixed obstacles, but as tensions to be navigated through participatory strategies, ongoing trust-building, and adaptive learning (Almirall & Wareham, 2008).

4.5.1 Stakeholder Engagement and Participation

Ensuring long-term, meaningful participation from diverse stakeholders—including craft makers, researchers, municipal authorities, and citizens—remains a central challenge. While co-creation processes (Section 3.2) fostered initial enthusiasm and generated important shared values, sustaining engagement over time requires attention to logistics, capacity, and emotional labour.

Craft makers in particular have expressed challenges in balancing their artistic practice with administrative and collaborative demands. Differing time horizons and expectations between institutional actors and self-employed creators sometimes led to misalignment. To address this, the HGLL emphasized low-barrier participation formats, informal site visits, and one-on-one conversations to better accommodate stakeholder needs and build interpersonal trust (Von Wirth et al., 2019).

4.5.2 Resource and Funding Limitations

The prototyping and testing of circular solutions—such as ceramic waste reuse or alternative energy kilns—require both time and material resources. While project funding has supported early experimentation, financial sustainability remains uncertain. Artists and makers frequently highlighted the importance of fair compensation, particularly when expected to contribute intellectual, creative, or physical labour to research and innovation efforts (Bason & Schneider, 2021).

To address this, HEPHAESTUS submitted two external funding applications (each for 50,000 DKK to the Danish State's Kunstfond) to help finance Living Lab activities in 2025. These applications are part of a broader effort to establish complementary funding channels that can secure continuity and equitable remuneration for all participants.

Infrastructural and Regulatory Complexity

Some HGLL activities—particularly those involving waste streams or energy systems—face regulatory hurdles that impact both timeline and feasibility. The Ødeland Crushing Machine Project, for example, required rigorous compliance with EU safety directives and materials testing (Section 4.2.1). Similarly, the Kiln with Waste Oil Firing initiative (Section 4.2.2) raised concerns around emissions and combustion control that required input from external institutions such as DTU.

Such issues highlight the value—but also the challenge—of integrating creative experimentation into systems that are regulated for safety and environmental protection. Living Labs must act as translational interfaces between innovation and regulation, navigating technical feasibility and socio-political constraints (Höflechner et al., 2022).

4.5.3 Navigating Between Heritage and Innovation

One of the more delicate tensions within the HGLL is the question of how to integrate emerging technologies—such as digital fabrication, AI, and podcasting—without undermining the integrity of traditional craft practices. Some artists have shown interest in using digital tools for communication, grant writing, or inspiration, but hesitate to integrate these tools directly into their creative process.

This signals a need for deeper exploration of what “technology” means in the context of craft, and how digital tools can enhance rather than dilute the meaning and materiality of heritage. The podcast initiative (Section 4.2.3), for instance, has been well received precisely because it leverages digital media as a storytelling device rather than a production tool—an approach more in line with the values of participating craft makers (Zumach & Portillo, 2020).

4.5.4 Overcoming Barriers Through Participatory Adaptation

HEPHAESTUS has adopted a series of strategies to respond constructively to these challenges, drawing on the NEB Toolbox principles—especially participatory processes, multi-level engagement, and a transdisciplinary approach (European Commission, 2024; Bason & Schneider, 2021):

- *Relational Stakeholder Engagement:* Through informal interviews, craft network participation, and event-based presence (e.g., ACAB Jubilee, BOFA Resource Day), the project team cultivated personal relationships and deeper listening practices.
- *Empowerment over Imposition:* Craft makers were invited to initiate or co-lead projects that aligned with their own creative or business trajectories. Of the seven ongoing HGLL initiatives, four emerged from maker-led concepts, reinforcing distributed ownership (Section 4.2).
- *Balancing Structure and Flexibility:* While offering frameworks for collaboration and decision-making, the project avoided rigid branding or activity mandates. As noted in the visual identity strategy (Section 4.4), this has helped maintain trust and creative freedom.
- *Practicing Mutual Benefit:* Learning from previous top-down efforts in the region, HEPHAESTUS prioritized reciprocity, ensuring that participation offered value—be it in the form of visibility, knowledge-sharing, material support, or access to policy platforms.
- *Iterative Learning and Reflexivity:* Trust-building is not a one-time act. The team continues to monitor feedback, refine approaches, and adjust timelines to remain sensitive to emerging needs and challenges (Schäpke et al., 2018).

By acknowledging and addressing these tensions head-on, the HGLL becomes not only a platform for sustainability experimentation, but also a living system of cultural negotiation, adaptation, and collaboration. These insights will be crucial in informing the evaluation phase (Section 5) and scaling efforts (Section 6), where the lessons of Bornholm can inform broader transformations in European craft ecosystems.

5.0 Evaluation

This section outlines the methodological framework used to assess the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) on Bornholm, building on the co-creation processes (Section 3), the ongoing implementation of Living Lab activities (Section 4), and the theoretical grounding provided by the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles (Section 2). As the HGLL moves from ideation to real-world experimentation, evaluation becomes essential not only for measuring progress, but also for capturing how the values of participation, sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetic innovation are enacted in practice. The evaluation approach recognizes that Living Labs operate in dynamic, context-dependent environments, where success is shaped by iterative learning and the quality of stakeholder engagement as much as by predefined outcomes. Accordingly, the following sections introduce the Harmonized Assessment Methodology (HAM) designed to monitor, reflect upon, and guide the adaptive development of the HGLL in line with its mission, values, and evolving challenges.

5.1 Methodological approach to assessment of the Living Labs

The evaluation of Living Labs (LLs) has gained increasing scholarly attention in recent years, with researchers such as Mulder et al. (2007), Salminen et al. (2011), Ståhlbröst (2012), Mastelic et al. (2015), Van Geenhuizen (2018), Bronson et al. (2021), Dekker et al. (2021), Vervoort et al. (2022), and Santonen (2024) emphasizing the importance of robust evaluation frameworks to ensure long-term viability and learning. These frameworks not only help identify strengths and weaknesses, but also guide improvement processes, enhance transparency, and support benchmarking efforts across LLs.

Evaluation also plays a formative role in supporting reflexivity within LLs. As Schuurman et al. (2016) note, LL assessment contributes to understanding the layered nature of LLs—including their organizational structures, socio-technical systems, and user involvement mechanisms—providing a foundation for iterative learning and adaptation. Importantly, these frameworks can help illuminate how co-created knowledge is translated into action and which systemic barriers still remain.

In the case of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) on Bornholm, a Harmonized Assessment Methodology (HAM) has been designed to support continuous monitoring of both processes and outcomes. The HAM is grounded in the principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB), particularly its emphasis on iterative, inclusive, and transdisciplinary approaches to transformation (Deserti & Puerari, 2025). Rather than evaluating projects solely by pre-defined deliverables or static Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the HAM adopts a dynamic approach centered on Process Indicators (PIs).

This aligns with Schuurman's (2015) assertion that LLs follow a quasi-experimental design, where both objectives and conditions evolve in response to real-world variables. Consequently, fixed KPIs often fail to capture the full complexity of LL processes. By contrast, PIs enable an assessment model that reflects the living, emergent nature of the HGLL—tracking not only “what” was achieved, but “how,” “with whom,” and “under what conditions.”

The HAM thus functions as a reflexive monitoring tool, allowing project partners to iteratively assess the impact and quality of co-creation, innovation, and community engagement. In alignment with NEB Toolbox guidance (European Commission, 2023), it captures qualitative and relational

dimensions of transformation—including social inclusion, aesthetic value, material circularity, and systems change—rather than reducing impact to quantitative outputs alone.

In M44, D5.5 will present the results of the HGLL evaluation in full, using the outlined PIs to measure how the Living Lab has supported Bornholm’s craft ecosystem in advancing sustainable tourism, material reuse, and circular economy objectives.

5.1.1 Evaluation Metrics and Process Indicators

As outlined in Figure 20 and further detailed in Table 3, the HGLL evaluation is structured around five core principles of Living Labs—Value, Realism, Influence, Openness, and Sustainability (Femmer et al., 2019). Each principle is linked to a set of process indicators, forming the foundation of the HAM. This structure reflects the values identified in D5.1 and carried forward into ongoing implementation (Section 4.2).

Moreover, the evaluation approach includes key social engagement indicators. Following Lucchesi & Rutkowski (2021), this includes tracking levels of participation, diversity of stakeholders, and depth of involvement in decision-making. Community satisfaction and perceived agency are also measured via surveys and interviews, while stakeholder mapping and partnership-building metrics help assess the strength and reach of the HGLL network (Leminen & Westerlund, 2012; Van Geenhuizen, 2018).

As described in Section 3.2, the co-creation workshops provided a foundation for building trust and participatory capacity, while Section 4.2 illustrates how those inputs have been carried into real-world experiments. By drawing on those sections, the evaluation framework links process and outcome, tracking how the HGLL evolves as a place-sensitive, stakeholder-driven space for innovation.

In this way, the HAM does not merely measure results—it supports learning, adjustment, and responsiveness, enabling the HGLL to adapt to shifting community needs, policy landscapes, and material conditions. It ultimately positions evaluation not as a final step, but as a continuous, embedded practice that helps cultivate resilience, inclusivity, and impact across the HEPHAESTUS network.

Figure 20: Living Lab's five essential principles (Femmer et al, 2019, p. 27)

Living Lab Principle	Focus	Process Indicator	Verification method	NEB Priority Alignment (Section 3.2)
Value	Ensuring the product/service/technology truly addresses user needs and offers meaningful benefits.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User Relevance & Satisfaction: % of participants who find solutions relevant. - Ease of Adoption: Ease of integrating lab's solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surveys, Focus groups, Interviews with craft-makers/stakeholders 	Sustainability (value to people and planet), Inclusion (participant agency)
Realism	Testing ideas in a real-world environment, involving actual Stakeholders, i.e. craftmakers, researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-Use Testing Ratio: Frequency and scale of real-life testing. - Authentic Stakeholder Engagement: Number of real users actively contributing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project logs, Observations, Attendance sheets 	Real-life Experimentation (core NEB testbed feature), Participation
Influence	Making sure different stakeholders' voices clearly shape final outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traceability of Ideas: User suggestions implemented. - Domain Expert Visibility: Expert needs integrated in final deliverables. 	Version control, Design logs, Stakeholder surveys	Participation (multi-level engagement), Influence (traceability)
Openness	Bringing multiple perspectives into the co-creation process, ensuring transparency and diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diversity of Perspectives: Range of stakeholder groups involved. - Shared Platforms & Access: Availability and use of open collaboration tools (WhatsApp Group, podcast etc.) 	Stakeholder mapping, Platform analytics, Open-access documents	Inclusion (diverse stakeholders), Transparency (open process)
Sustainability	Embedding ecological, social, and economic considerations into the innovation process.	Materials Reuse & Waste Reduction: Through BOFA, access to waste material is provided	Material audits, Lifecycle analysis, Business model viability assessments	Sustainability (environmental and socio-economic), Circularity

		- Long-Term Viability: Number of solutions with feasible business models (T3.1, sustainable business models)		
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Table 3: Living Lab Principles and Process Indicators

6. Policy dialogue and scale-up

The policy dialogue and scale-up potential of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) is most concretely embodied in the formation of the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank, as detailed in D5.4. Functioning as both a continuation and evolution of Maker's Island Bornholm, the Think Tank serves as the primary coordination organ for sustaining Living Lab outcomes, supporting scale-up, and anchoring Bornholm's craft sector in broader circular economy transitions.

Crucially, the Think Tank is not conceived as a static advisory body but rather as a dynamic, distributed platform—deeply rooted in the participatory methodologies of the HGLL (Sections 3.2 and 4.2) and shaped by the trust-building processes outlined in Section 4.5. Its core objective is to preserve and activate the knowledge, relationships, and policy relevance generated through HGLL experimentation. Through regular working groups and stakeholder assemblies, the Think Tank enables cross-sector knowledge transfer and co-creation of sustainable policy pathways.

The Think Tank also formalizes a structural interface between grassroots experimentation and institutional scale-up. Actors like BOFA, Destination Bornholm, Business Center Bornholm, the Royal Danish Academy, and ACAB continue their involvement as institutional anchors, ensuring continuity between local craft innovation and regional policy agendas. Moreover, by incorporating external input—such as comparative insights from the Bassano ecosystem—the Think Tank positions Bornholm as a replicable node within broader EU green economy networks.

The Think Tank's roadmap (D5.4, Section 4) offers a forward-looking framework for policy-oriented interventions, including:

- Strategic support for circular business models,
- Continued investment in lifelong learning for craft practitioners,
- Formal advocacy for craft-aligned sustainability policies,
- Replicable coordination mechanisms to guide future Living Lab initiatives.

Together, these efforts create a transitory structure that not only outlives the HEPHAESTUS project itself but actively shapes policy environments conducive to sustainable, place-based craft ecosystems across Europe.

7. Conclusion

The HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL) has emerged as a dynamic and context-sensitive platform for experimentation, shaped by iterative engagement, grounded co-creation, and material innovation. Anchored in Bornholm’s unique position as a “test island” for circular transition, the HGLL has shown how artistic practice, public infrastructure, and policy visions can converge to generate tangible, place-based solutions.

From the Crushing Machine Project to the Slow Tourism initiatives, the activities detailed in this deliverable demonstrate how New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles—sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion—can be made operational through collaborative innovation. These initiatives have not only translated theoretical frameworks into lived experimentation but have done so while honouring the social, cultural, and economic realities of the craft ecosystem.

A core strength of the HGLL lies in its flexible, trust-building methodology. Co-creation has unfolded through symposia, focus groups, and informal interactions, enabling the project to remain attuned to shifting needs. The adoption of a Harmonized Assessment Methodology (HAM) centred on process indicators has ensured a reflexive approach to monitoring—one that values iteration and learning over fixed outcomes.

Several cross-cutting insights have emerged:

- *Material Circularity and Craft Innovation:* Experimental reuse of waste materials has highlighted the potential—and regulatory complexity—of embedding circularity in artisan production.
- *Stakeholder Empowerment and Inclusion:* Building trust through relational engagement, clear communication, and distributed leadership has been essential to overcoming historical frictions and co-developing responsive activities.
- *Systemic Alignment and Policy Integration:* The policy dialogue and scale-up strategy, supported by the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank (Section 6; see D5.4), marks a critical next phase. Here, insights from the HGLL will inform broader regional and European sustainability pathways, aligning experimentation with long-term governance and institutional support.

Looking ahead, the HGLL is not only a proof of concept but a working prototype for how local craft systems can lead innovation in circular transitions. Its participatory ethos, grounded in care, creativity, and community, offers a replicable model for how Living Labs can navigate complexity while maintaining fidelity to local identity and values.

Ultimately, the greatest legacy of the HGLL may not be any single activity, but rather the collective capacity it nurtures—a capacity to imagine, test, and co-create futures rooted in sustainability, heritage, and inclusive transformation.

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